

COLLABORATIVE BLENDED LEARNING IN THE FINE ARTS USING SOCIAL NETWORK PLATFORMS

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Abstract:

This Project shows some collaborative Blended Learning experiences in which the on-line tool for social networks Ning was used as a complement to the presental teaching in Fine Arts. The main topic was the study and experimentation of strategies of collective creation in the two subjects in which these experiences were carried out. The project took place in the Faculty of Fine Arts, University Miguel Hernández, during 2008-09 and 2009-10 academical years.

The main aim of these experiences was to work the key aspects in collective creation processes with the students through collaborative methodological strategies.

The methodology covers these four aspects:

1. Promoting collaborative learning through the use of a tool that boosts participation and interaction among students, widening the framework of presental teaching.
2. Practising and deepening in the search, selection and analysis of information in the Internet to encourage students critical thinking with regard to the use of new technologies and information management.
3. Creating collective files of information that allow the sharing of text, image, video and sound in order to improve knowledge and points of view.
4. Experimenting and sharing of collective creation processes through sharing ideas, public follow-up of the process of creation of projects within a team work and public exhibition of results.

Webs of the Project:

<http://arteycreacioncolectiva.ning.com><http://estrategiascreativas09.ning.com><http://estrategiascreativas10.ning.com>

Keywords:

Web 2.0, Social Networking, Blended learning, collaborative learning, Fine Arts.

COLLABORATIVE BLENDED LEARNING IN THE FINE ARTS USING SOCIAL NETWORKS PLATFORMS

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Abstract

This Project shows some collaborative Blended Learning experiences in which the on-line tool for social networks Ning was used as a complement to the presential teaching in Fine Arts. This experience was carried out in the Faculty of Fine Arts, University Miguel Hernández, during 2008-09 and 2009-10 academical years. The two subjects in which they made the experience had as its theme the study and testing of collective creation strategies.

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INTRODUCTION

This paper deals with and analyses some teaching experiences of blended learning through collaborative teaching and learning processes done in the Fine Arts degree at Altea's Faculty of Fine Arts, University Miguel Hernández - Elche (Alicante). These experiences took place during 2008-09 y 2009-10 academical years related to two subjects dealing with collective creation.

The aim of these experiences was to explore the possibility of different ways of collaborative work through the use of ICT tools combined with aspects of presential teaching in order to develop abilities and competences common in a Fine Arts degree, according to the *Tunning* project in the European Higher Education Area (EHEA).

This paper is divided into four sections. The first one deals with the conceptual framework, in which we deal with some key concepts related to collaborative learning in blended learning within Internet Society context.

The second section deals with practical cases done in this experience: showing the context, the proposals, aims to be reached, methodologies used. Finally, we offer an assessment of the experiences carried out.

1. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

1.1. Key competences of EHEA within Network Society

Nowadays, the World is characterized by an increasing complexity, marked by factors such as accelerated technological advances, excess of information, economic globalization or virtuality in culture. In this scenario, the Internet, Information and Communication Technologies (ICT), and their evolution towards Web 2.0 are taking more and more prominence. They have an influence on all daily life areas and have become in tools for the social change. The Internet makes possible an increase in the information flow, generating a shared knowledge and helping to create new ways of self-organization and power redistribution. These aspects make up what is called Network Society[1].

The new challenges arisen by this context make that all educational levels have to rethink their organizational structures and methodologies. Within higher education, these reforms started to build up at a political level as of Bologna Declaration and the setting up of European Higher Education Area (EHEA) framework [2]. Nevertheless, norms have no effect if there is not a change of mind in all the agents involved in this process.

The key element of this reform, at a pedagogical level, is changing the model; this is, student-centred learning, opposite to the traditional model, which revolved around the lecturer. This new educational model is based on pedagogical theories linked to social *constructivism*, considering student's motivation and active attitude the key aspect in the learning process [3]. Taking into account these aspects, European norms of the EHEA define eight key competences that must be acquired by the students [4].

Of all these key competences, we would like to point out some that are not usually considered a priority in a Fine Arts studies; however, we have tried to work those specifically in our educational experiences. These competences are "oral and writing skills in Spanish", "digital competence", "learning to learn" and "social, and civic competences". The first two appear as transversal objectives in the Spanish *White Book of Bachelor Degrees in Fine Arts, Design and Restoration* (ANECA, 2004:385) [5]; however, teaching practice tends to take them for granted, and pays no attention to them in any of the subjects. This involves graduates will lack of some abilities, which involves effects in their future professional development. The other two competences together with "competence in foreign languages" are not even considered in the White Book or in many of the teaching plans of new Grades in Fine Arts. We think this exclusion is relevant.

We think it is relevant to remember some aspects of the definitions given by the EU of these key competences, since they are issues we have worked in a specific way in the teaching projects discussed in this paper.

"**digital competence**" is defined as:

Digital competence involves the confident and critical use of Information Society Technology (IST) for work, leisure and communication. It is underpinned by basic skills in ICT: the use of computers to retrieve, assess, store, produce, present and exchange information, and to communicate and participate in collaborative networks via the Internet.

"**learning to learn**" is defined as:

The ability to pursue and persist in learning. Individuals should be able to organise their own learning, including through effective management of time and information, both individually and in groups. [...]. It means gaining, processing and assimilating new knowledge and skills as well as seeking and making use of guidance. Learning to learn engages learners to build on prior learning and life experiences in order to use and apply knowledge and skills in a variety of contexts – at home, at work, in education and training.

With regard to "learning to learn" competence, it is emphasized the importance of students use vital experiences and previous learning, together with the importance of motivation and self-discipline in order to generate autonomous learning. Finally, it is relevant the value of teamwork and the ability of students to self evaluate their own work.

On the other hand, **Civic competence** refers to **personal, interpersonal and intercultural competence**. This competence highlights the importance of developing abilities for the participation and engagement in social environments, and also the development of abilities for solving conflicts.

1.2 From presential teaching to blended learning in Fine Arts Degree

Fine Arts studies, until these days, in Spain, have mainly been focused in presential teaching, with a predominance of practical teaching over theoretical one. 80% of credits in this degree are usually practical ones. This involves smaller groups of students per class. This fact together with the kind of works done (usually based on development of personal projects proposed by the students) favours a personalised teaching. These aspects are already very close to models of *teaching learning*, which places Fine Arts studies in a clear privileged situation for the educational reform.

Nevertheless, with regard to the use of digital technology in Fine Arts degrees, they are paradoxical situations. On the one side, we find students and lecturers profiles completely against the use of new technologies. They demand learning solely based in analogical procedures and techniques common to traditional subjects in the Fine Arts: drawing, painting, sculpture, and engraving. Simultaneously, profiles of students and lecturers that make an intensive and specialised use of new technologies as main working tools can be found. The latter are usually interested in design and audiovisual aids. This situation makes student groups are heterogeneous with regard to their abilities.

This characteristic demonstrates a kind of *digital division*, whose origin is not only related to age or "digital natives" [6] but also to the abilities of the agents involved with regard to the use and better use of technology, and their ability to build up meaningful and useful knowledge with them. Duart (2010) [7], who has studied *digital division* in higher education, states that this division may be found among technological uses done by lecturers and students. Besides, that division may be found among universities, according to the uses they provide of new technologies as a means of knowledge and, therefore, the possibilities they allow to their community.

Furthermore, Duart proposes five ways of using the Internet in the classroom (Duart *et al*, 2008: 224-226) [8]. They include a mere administrative use, resources of teaching support and Internet uses as a teaching supplement, and a teaching model strictly virtual, non presential. According to this classification, our teaching proposal aims to be what Duart calls (in Spanish) *hybrid training* (Duart *et al*, 2008: 227) [9]. For this author and his collaborators, *hybrid training* is the training in which presential and non presential activity appear as an **integrated** and **undivided continuum**. This type of teaching is considered a very valuable tool, since it allows great transformation during the learning process through the use of technology. In this training model, it is important to highlight as a key innovative element with regard to the presential process the use of the Internet to make possible that activities can keep developing outside the presential classroom.

Considering education as an open process is a common idea in many contemporary artistic practices that understand the creative process, or even one's own work, as a permanent evolution; this is, without a conclusive form, a continuum in which the borders between art and life shade off. These aspects have abundantly been dealt with from both art's theory [10] and practice. We can already find examples since artistic *avant-garde* times (as in Dadaist Schwitters' Merzbaus), or many pieces of work following anti-form or conceptual trends (such as *Informalismo*, *Fluxus*, the *Arte Povera* or the recent *Relational Art*, as well as some *Net Art* practices). From a conceptual perspective, this parallelism is really interesting. We think they open an interesting field of possibilities in order to explore ways of artistic teaching through technology; they do not only focus in technical aspects but also work conceptual aspects in a coherent way and look for a mutual adequacy.

1.3 Collaborative learning within Web 2.0 and social networks contexts

The evolution from Web 1.0 to Web 2.0 [11] has involved a substantial change in the way of using both technology and the Internet. **Web 1.0** followed the outline of traditional mass media, such as television, in which information was unidirectionally broadcasted, creating a vertical hierarchy of one sender to many passive recipients. **Web 2.0 or social Web** proposes a different model: information circulates in horizontal creating user networks that share, interact and collaborate with each other. Thus, a new kind of user appears. These users have the capacity of producing and altering contents, the so-called *prosumers*. This phenomenon has generated an exponential increase in information and contents circulating on the Internet, creating what some call "infoxication" or "information overload". This circumstance suggests the need of training on digital capacities in order to know how to do searches and discriminate useful information. The following step in this evolution is what some call **Web 3.0 or semantic web**. This would be based on data or metadata; however, this issue still has some technical difficulties that slow its development.

Web 2.0 typical tools could be grouped according to the functions they allow: a) generating contents using different formats (such as *Youtube*, *Flickr*, or *Slideshare*), b) generating and publishing their contents (blogs, wikis, Web sites), c) retrieving information (through labelling or RSS), and d) communicating and collaborating (social networks). Of all of these, **social networks** are the ones that have had a greater expansion during the past few years, they have become a truly social phenomenon. These web 2.0 tools, when combined, allow users to create efficient “personal learning environments” (PLE), which are very useful in education. Social networks are starting to have a prominent role due to the possibilities that they offer for collaborative build-up of knowledge. They encourage an active participation of students and help them to link their vital experiences with learning. All these aspects fall clearly within *constructivist* tradition of learning [12] and are updated with the new theories of *connectivism* by George Siemens, who is based on the idea that our knowledge resides on the connections we form with people and information, often mediated or facilitated with technology [13].

Web 2.0 involves a revolution affecting uses of digital technology in education; it accelerates the need of changes in the educational model. In 2008, Duarte (Duarte *et al.*, 2008: 21) [14] already warned about some paradoxical aspects of the uses of ICT in a university environment. He referred to the imbalance between an intensive use of the ICT by members of the university community with regard to extra-academic purposes and the little use of it in the building-up of meaningful learning processes; in most cases, this is limited to a search of information, communication or helping with documentation, which would correspond to an educational model 1.0. Exponential growth of social networks, especially among the youth for the past two years in Spain [15], seems to increase this imbalance. However, there are some exceptions that tend to be called “experimental activities”.

In any case, nowadays, some movement in all educational spheres from primary education to higher education has started. It aims to promote an educational model that could be called **education 2.0**. These experiences try to integrate characteristic tools of web 2.0 into the learning process. In many cases, these coincide in the necessity of stressing in EHEA's key competences abovementioned. A recurrent trait in many of these education 2.0 experiences tends to be the importance of integrating learning in real contexts or daily life factors, which often blurs the border between formal and informal learning [16]. We point out this aspect since it has been dealt with in the educational experiences presented in this paper.

Recently, Juan José de Haro has published an essay on the use of social networks in education [17]. He does an exhaustive analysis about social network tools and their uses in educational experiences during the past few years. This author offers a list of characteristics that identify education 2.0, divided into: **attitudes** (altruism, collaboration and respect), **abilities** (management of one's own knowledge, creative thinking, critical thought), and **competences** (1-research, assessment and selection of information sources, planning of strategies for research, processing of data and generation of results; 2- knowledge of digital tools in order to collaborate with others; 3- Production of digital objects of various types or formats; 4- communication with other, in order to get informed and create knowledge).

Before finishing this section, we would like to point out another relevant conceptual aspect in the experiences carried out. It is the **difference between collaborative learning and cooperative learning**. There is a debate and terminological confusion on this topic. Panitz [18] suggested a clear difference between both concepts in 1996, and we offer a summary here:

Collaborative learning happens when two or more people work jointly to define a meaning or improve some competence. There is a sharing of responsibility among group members. It is based upon consensus building through cooperation by group members. It allows development of student's autonomy.

On the other hand, **cooperative learning** also involves group learning but it is teacher-centred, who organises the tasks to be done in order to achieve specific goals. The teacher designs in a prescriptive way steps to be followed. This kind of learning, even involving group tasks, considerably limits a personalised learning.

2. TEACHING PROJECTS

The project of teaching innovation that we are presenting dealt with some collaborative teaching and learning experiences carried out in two subjects in Altea's Fine Arts degree (according to pre-Bologna Process academic plan), University Miguel Hernández – Elche, during 2008-09, 2009-10 academic years. . These two subjects were theoretical-practical and their contents were related to methodologies of creative processes and collective creation.

Although these experiences were carried out within the framework of the old academic plan, they use a teaching-learning approach. The general aim of this experience was to link one on-line tool to artistic presential teaching, as blended learning, through the use of collaborative learning. These experiences aimed to promote an active participation of students, together with their autonomy and responsibility in the learning process.

The main **aim** of this experience was to line one on-line tool to artistic presential teaching to see different key aspects in collective creation processes in order to deepen in some methodological strategies and broaden their approaches.

The specific aims were:

- 1 . **Fostering collaborative learning** through the use of a tool that promotes participation and interaction among students, broadening the framework of presential teaching.
- 2.- **Practising and deepening in the search, selection and analysis of information on Internet** in order to encourage their critical judgement with regard to the use of new technologies and information management.
3. **Generating collective archives of information** that allow them to share text, image, video and sound, so knowledge and points of view can be increased.
- 4 . **Experimenting and sharing collective creation processes** through sharing ideas, public following of the process of preparation of team projects and public exhibition of the results.

2.1. Teaching Context

The projects we are going to present in this paper were done in the Fine Arts degree. The Faculty is located in Altea (Alicante), a small coastal town, with little cultural activity but where tourism is an important asset. This Faculty belongs to the University Miguel Hernández - Elche (Alicante), which has several campuses in Alicante province. The only degree in Altea's campus is Fine Arts, which causes some isolation, making difficult the contact with other disciplines and limiting the access to infrastructures and other resources of the university. In this context, considering the use of technology allows us to broaden access to information, this is, to go beyond the limits of this peripheral geographical space, which is far from cultural centres.

As we have previously said, Fine Arts studies are presential and practical studies. This makes possible a personalized contact, which enables projects that would be difficult in other contexts. These characteristics ease the use of teaching-learning methodologies proposed by EHEA's framework, since they create a suitable context for the interaction and personalized follow-up of students by their lecturer. Also, those methodologies help the students in their relationships and learning collaborations among each other. These aspects helped to make possible both an active use of digital tools and an extension of the presential space.

With regard to student's profile, it is interesting to note that they were heterogeneous both in age and abilities; in some groups, the age was between 20 and 60. Although, the vast majority of students could be considered "digital natives", it can be observed that most of them lack of digital competences and access to the Internet outside the Faculty. The latter is mainly due to the fact that many students live in shared flats with other students and they lack of 3G mobiles when the experience was carried out. Since Fine Arts studies are essentially practical, it can be seen students had some lack of theoretical knowledge that affected the development of abilities required for theoretical research (such as search for bibliographical data, conceptual analysis or writing and oral skills, and a low knowledge of a foreign language). We aimed to deal with these issues in the experiences presented here.

On the other hand, it is also important to mention that, generally, Fine Arts' students tend to have a motivated and reasonably active profile. This aspect was considerably increased with the use of a digital tool that showed in a transparent way the processes, generating a positive competence amongst students and making possible interaction among them.

Another relevant fact was the initial reluctance to do collaborative projects. This reluctance tends to show a high percentage amongst Fine Arts' students. This can be due to the myth of the artist as an individual creator, boosted by some sectors in the artistic system; however, these days, this is considered both anachronistic and not very practical. Nowadays, many professional perspectives for Fine Arts graduates involve team work and network abilities. Creating an artistic installation, a public wall, a design or audiovisual project, are tasks that require a profile closer to a producer or mediator than to an individual creator.

Finally, this experience was done linked to the initiative of generating a Group of innovative teaching, in order to do some experiences using online tools, as a complement to presential teaching. This was helpful in order to work with possibilities that can be established as on-line resources in presential teaching, within the adaptation process to new Degree (*grado*) and Master academic plans. This experience became a truly blended process, in which both practices (presential and virtual) were integrated; it was difficult to differentiate practice from process. This first and humble experience started with a basic training course on free web tools. This was promoted by the Faculty, but IT service did not provide any support. Given this situation, a small number of lecturers started to do some experiences in their classes, without any kind of coordination. Results presented in this paper are based on experiences done by the same lecturer in two of her subjects during 2008-09 y 2009-10.

2.2 Means and Tools used

With regard to technological and organizational infrastructures of the academic institution where we did the experiences, it is relevant to point out some characteristics that determined our choice of tools and methodologies of the projects presented in this paper. The academic institution has a computer room, with enough computers for students during presential teaching hours, but not always enough during free-access time. The biggest problem in order to do teaching experiences with digital tools was the limited provisions by the IT service of the university. This academic institution has not got yet any kind of digital platform that allows its members to manage collaborative activities, such as wikis, forum or debates. This issues, is not only a technical one but also reflects a strategic deficiency about teaching possibilities with digital technology. This university's present web provides services considered 1.0; they are practically unidirectional and hardly interactive (institutional and pedagogical information, documents, e-mail and some but limited tools for tasks online –for essays' submissions).

Taking into account this situation and since we wanted students could do a collaborative work, we considered some options. Finally, we chose the vertical network platform Ning as the **web tool used** to develop these projects. This platform was used as private; this is, only for its members. It was public once the experience had finished, so the process could be seen.

The reasons to choose this tool were:

- It was an **open source and free tool**. The university did not provide any similar platform allowing similar activities or technical support.
- It was **easy to use and manage** both for the lecturer/administrator and students/users.
- It allowed us to easily manage **degrees of privacy**.
- It allowed us to **group different tools** linked to one web space.
- It offered **versatility to integrate different means** within an attractive and clear design.

The experiences showing the use of the social network platform allowed a fluent and permanent contact among students, and between them and their lecturer. This facilitated the follow-up of the working process and the accomplishment of collaborative tasks. It was especially practical in the activities for the second proposal, in which teams were formed by two or three students, besides keeping in contact with the rest of the group. For these reasons, it is understandable that this technological tool was used for a blended learning.

2.3 Teaching project 1. Collaborative archive about collective creation. Subject “Strategies of collective creation”, PhD course.

2.3.1. Subject:

“Strategies of collective creation” PhD course within the PhD programme: “Contemporary Artistic Territories” Degree of Fine Arts. Academical year 2008-09, 24 students.

2.3.2. Description of the Proposal:

The proposal made to the students is the building a collective archive on various practices and concepts linked to collective creation within contemporary visual arts. Information had to be searched on the Internet and it could be in any means allowing its digital archive –text, photograph or video. Based on this shared information, each student had to write a personal and argued report on one of the documented concepts or examples.

2.3.3. Aims:

This first course within postgraduate studies aims to initiate the students into research. For this reason, this activity was planned to make the students search for information, select it, sort it out, analyse it, share it and offer a personal assessment.

This task aimed to practise the following abilities and skills:

- Ability to search, analyse, and summarise information.
- Writing skills and communicative ability.
- Ability to use technological tools.
- Ability to offer critical thought.
- Conceptual knowledge on artistic referents.
- Ability to carry out collaborative work.

2.3.4. Methodology:

The said digital tool together with its functionality was presented at the beginning of the course. Didactic material on basic concepts was given. This material was theoretical (about specific topics), technical (methodologies dealing with search for information in digital and analogical medium; preparation of theoretical works), and technological (dealing with the proper use of this digital tool). All this information was linked to Ning digital platform, under the tabs “documents”, “tools” or “bibliography”.

Tool’s homepage presented the subject and offered a description of both the subject and the activity students had to carry out.

Ning platform <http://arteycreacioncolectiva.ning.com> was used as a virtual space that Could be used both in presential classes and by students working autonomously. Every student had a personal space in the platform and all participated in the forum.

Ning forum was used as a repository, containing all the information stored by the students, and classified according to topics and basic concepts. The topics dealt with the following types of collective creation: intermittent collaboration, teams, groups, and collectives. The basic concepts dealt with strategies for collective creation: collective authorship, collective communication, game, collage strategy, creative techniques of organisation. The forum also offered one category for asking questions on techniques or methodology, and another so-called “free forum” for the students to ask other questions they could have.

Besides using the forum and personal blogs, students could publish events in order to share their interests with the rest of the group.

The events widget help to remind students about course’s scheduled activities, but they could also extra-academic events related to the subject. Chat tool was also activated, so students could communicate among themselves outside teaching hours.

Students’ activity was structured in the following tasks and phases:

1.- Searching and discriminating quality information in the net. This helped to use searching and critical thought abilities. They had to value relevance of the information and also had to use different kinds of engine searchers.

2. Searching and tagging information to help the collective use of the information. This train their summary ability, writing skills, and collective responsibility within the group.
3. Linking various kinds of files in the digital platform, according to their category in the forum: text, photographs, videos, links. It enabled the improvement of skills in the use of basic digital tools.
4. Discussing entries done by other students and helping among themselves in order to improve the quality of the given information or complement it.
5. Finally, doing a personal theoretical work about one of the examples or concepts studied. In their essay, students had to discuss and assess specific aspects which are characteristic of the various relevant aspects of collective creation. Each student uploaded their work in their blog within Ning.

2.4 Teaching project 2: Development of a collaborative project for a specific place. Subject “Creative Strategies”. Degree (pre-Bologna Process)

2.4.1. Subject:

“Creative Strategies”. This is a compulsory subject in 4th year, with 3 theoretical credits and 6 practical credits. This was a compulsory subject. Students were divided into three groups and this experience was only done in one of the groups. This project was carried out in two academical years, during their last term. Academical year 2008-09, 16 students which formed 8 teams of 2 people each. Academical year 2009-10, 18 students which formed 6 teams of 3 people each.

2.4.2. Description of the Project:

Development of a collaborative project for a specific place done by 2-3 people teams.

- The task involved choosing and documenting about one real and *site specific*, accessible to all the members of the team. Documentation had to include conceptual, historical, functional and technical information of the place.
- Based on that documentation, each team had to choose an appropriate topic for that place and design a project of artistic intervention, which would dialogue both with the space and the receptors of the project. Students had to take into account the civic component; in this case, they are meaningful connotations created by the project, and how it could affect the context in the future.
- Proposal’s design included: written and visual description, maps of the location, plans of the project, budget, project schedule, and any other technical requisite that they may need such as technical details or authorisations.
- A version in paper and another one in digital format (power point) had to be made for the final project; the digital format version was presented in the class, followed by a debate with the other students. The material used during the process together with final results was uploaded in Ning space allocated for each team as the binnacle of their activity.
- The project was presented in the class together with a personal assessment on process and results.

2.4.3. Aims:

The aim of this final year subject is to achieve knowledge and to develop creative strategies common to the artistic activity. It involves maturity and fluency in the use of basic resources and deals with more complex problems of organizational nature and also related to the real context.

This task aimed to practise the following abilities and skills:

- Ability to search, analyse, and summarise information.
- Communicative ability, and writing and oral skills.
- Communicative ability through audiovisual projects.
- Ability to develop and manage artistic projects.
- Ability to use technological tools.
- Ability to offer critical thought.
- Conceptual knowledge on artistic referents.
- Ability to interact within a real socio-cultural context (civic competence).

2.4.4. Methodology:

The said digital tool together with its functionality was presented at the beginning of the course. Didactic material on basic concepts was given. It involved giving them all the information needed on creation and development of projects, planning, budget, and presentations. Also, it involved giving the students basic theory about team work: conflict management, roles and phases.

All this information was linked to Ning digital platform, under the tabs “documents”, “tools” or “bibliography”.

Tool’s homepage presented the subject and offered a description of both the subject and the activity students had to carry out.

Ning groups created for these activities had the following http addresses:

<http://estrategiascreativas09.ning.com>

<http://estrategiascreativas10.ning.com>

Methodology used for Ning platform was similar to the one described for the first proposal, except for the forum. In this proposal, the forum was used to create each team binnacles, in which discussion lines dealing with aspects and phases of the work were open. Each group managed its own space, which made them to develop negotiation abilities and consensus in order to organise them. The fact that all the other teams could see the activities of the others helped them to learn from themselves.

The events widget was used in a similar way to the experience already described.

Chat tool was relevant in this case. It permitted simultaneous communication among students outside teaching hours. Since teams had few members, it was a very useful tool.

Students’ activity was structured in the following tasks and phases:

1. Organization of team work, planning, ways of communications, assignment of roles.
2. Search of information about the place, taking into account all the relevant aspects. This made students use several ways of documentation: libraries, Internet, interviews, local archives, newspaper and periodical libraries, interviewing neighbours, etc.
3. Choice and contextualization of the topic for the chosen location. This involved assessment, negotiation and consensus among the members of the team in order to reach agreements.
4. Design of a proposal of artistic project in the location studied. It was important to pay attention to the integration of the work in its location and the conditions for its reception. Proposal’s design included a written and visual description, location maps, plans of the project, budget, project schedule planning, and any other technical requisite that they may need such as technical details or authorisations.

A version in paper and another one in digital format (power point) had to be made for the final project; the digital format version was presented in the class, including an assessment on process and results. The material used during the process together with final results was uploaded in Ning space allocated for each team as the binnacle of their activity.

3. ASSESMENT OF RESULTS

Finally, we are going to mention some ideas and assessment originated in these experiences. We consider they are not conclusive; on the contrary, they are thoughts that can provide discussion and debate. Also, we deem them to be essential during the experimentation process, which is understood as a laboratory in open process allowing the generation of future experiences.

Students participating in the projects were given questionnaires at the end of the academic year. They were asked about several aspects and these were they assessments:

a) **With regard to the tool usability and the information received for its use.** Answers were highly satisfactory. They emphasized it as a simple tool easy to use. Difficulties were not due to technical aspects but organizational ones, specifically with regard to choosing criteria for classifying and filing information.

b) **With regard to advantages and difficulties obtained in collaborative work.**

Students doing the first project presented in this paper, worked collaboratively. However, students doing the second project worked in teams and were more explicit about their difficulties.

A vast majority stated that the work had been useful because it allowed them to cover more aspects and information, complementing each other lack in their skills and knowledge; it also made them be critical, which helped them to reach a better result. With regard to difficulties, nearly all of them pointed out that the most difficult was to reach agreements and take decisions about the form. Most of the students agreed that they had really enjoyed working together with other students, even they had had fun. In general, they described the experience as very satisfactory.

On this regard, it is relevant to mention that a similar exercise had been done in the previous year without using any digital tool. On those occasions, it was common to point out as a difficulty the coordination amongst the members of a team. In these last experiences, due to the possibility of combining both synchronic and asynchronous tools, these problems was considerably reduced.

In relation to this, it is significant enough to mention that teams that had more difficulties to meet outside presential classes were the ones that made a greater and, in general, better use of this tool (better organized and applying critical thought). It seems it could be in this way, since they had a higher dependence on a better use in order to obtain results.

Besides these students' opinions, we would like to stress others we consider relevant with regard to the experiences carried out:

- Advantages of using blended learning, compared to only presential teaching.

It favours more contact and follow-up of processes between lecturer and student, and also a greater collaboration among students.

On the other hand, the possibility of visualising processes as a diary, visible to everybody, makes students get more involved; it creates a positive competence and a greater rigor in each phase of the work. This aspects, which is generally positive, may be a negative element for some students and that should be something the tutor has to be aware of and manage accordingly.

- In our opinion, Blended learning offers many possibilities in the Fine Arts degree. It helps to work transversal competences needed for the professional development of the future graduates. Of these competences, we highlight digital competences and all the aspects related to them, such as skills for searches and critical analysis of information, ability to work as a team, ability to create networking, ability to express themselves by communication through different means and using different languages (from verbal to audiovisual).

Furthermore, we consider this methodology is very useful in order to think about one's own creative processes. It helps following the processes and their visualisation as a diary, which can be shared or used privately. Also, it is very useful to learn to manage, plan and organise work.

- One of the more relevant aspects is that **blended learning contributes to understand learning process as an open and continuous laboratory**, in both time and space. It works outside the classroom space and can go beyond teaching environment, linking the learning with vital experiences.

- With regard to the **use of Ning network as a tool for educational experiences:**

a) A very positive trait is its **easy management and its simplicity to visualise the activity** in the various phases of the work: group activity, student's individual activity, and group activity. It can be added that the tool was "transparent" and adequate for the aims planned.

b) The fact of using an Internet tool that could be public created interesting debates on a critical and responsible use of the Internet. It made students question about copyright, private data, or private policies with regard to tools of public use, and limits between public and private issues. All this helped students to acquire digital competences and to think about conceptual issues related to subject's syllabus.

c) Related to b) and due to the recent policy change by Ning administrators, as of August 2010 the tool stopped being of free payment, some debates arose about difficulties created by the use of external tools to educational environment. On this issue two questions arose. The first one linked to a need for commitment by the educational community to guarantee data security and privacy. The other was about the loss of control about knowledge in academic institutions.

- In these experiences, especially in the second one, **students were the focal point of the project**. They had to decide throughout the process about topics, places, where and how look for information, how classify it and how to use it in order to generate a project linked to a real context with which they had to create some kind of interaction. Besides, they had to learn how to organised and plan their work to meet deadlines and fulfil aims.

Finally, some thoughts about university management with regard to the experiences carried out.

- **Need of university's involvement and commitment with regard to introduction and development of new technologies**. Clearly, the experiences carried out are what Tony Bates (2001) [19] call practices of the "lonely soldier" when one lecturer on their own does innovative teaching experiences with technology but without the support of the academic institution. This task is, according to Bates, a good means to make lecturers start to use new technologies; it would be useful if it would be possible to mobilise higher hierarchy in order to start to rethink about the need of an structured organisation, well planned and with the necessary means. In the long run, as Bates puts it, the "lonely soldier" will be an expensive and inefficient method.

The only way of obtaining quality results (with a good cost-efficiency) is through project management of well planned projects, with clear aims linked to a sufficient funding, done with a good professional team, and specific funding and production plans. Also, it should be added a change of mind, in terms of being closer to ways of relations in web 2.0 (more horizontal and democratic). This change of mind seems a bit far of present management organs in Spanish universities, although some progress has been done in this regard.

- **Need to value and acknowledge teaching experiences using new technologies**. This is one of the subjects to make up within Spanish university. These kind of teaching activities have little acknowledgment in internal quality accreditations by universities and by the Spanish National Agency for Quality Accreditation; despite this Agency include them as required transversal competences in nearly all the new degrees. We think a change should be made in this regard in the short term in order to help to make a better use and a greater development of these practices.

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